

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT FAILURE ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH BEAM

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SUMMARY: As concluded experimentally on low-velocity impact behavior of sandwich beam subjected to the cylindrical impactor, the core material and face sheets dominate the failure modes. The main failure pattern of sandwich beam with lower density core material is shear cracks in foam (Mode I), whereas crushed in core and damage in the top face sheets right underneath the impactor (Mode II) when core material density is higher. Finite element software ABAQUS is used, and maximum stress failure criterion and a modified stiffness degradation method are adopted to investigate the initiation of failure, the failure modes and post-failure behavior of sandwich beam. The numerical results are in good agreement with experimental results. Parametric studies, including stiffness ratio of face sheets to core and ratio of impactor diameter to simple support span, are also conducted

KEYWORDS: Impact, sandwich beam, post-failure behavior, stiffness degradation, maximum stress failure criterion.

INTRODUCTION

Owing to the advantages of lightweight and high bending strength, the composite sandwich materials play an important role in today's industry. In marine engineering, more and more ships of small sizes such as fishing boats, and yachts, use sandwich panels in ship hull construction. However, inadvertent collision during the fabrication process, wave impact during sailing, and so on, may induce damage of sandwich structures and cause significant reduction of the stiffness and strength of materials. Thus, further understanding of impact loading, impact response and impact damage of composite sandwich is necessary for the sake of safety.

Much work has been done on impact resistance and impact tolerance of composite sandwich panels as in Ref. [1]-[3]. However, because of the complication of contact behavior between the projectile and sandwich panels, it is very difficult to predict the impact behavior by establishing mathematical model. An well-known approach, proposed by Tan and Sun in Ref. [4], considered for determining the impact response is, firstly, to measure the local contact behavior of the panel by static indentation test; secondly, to use this experimental results in conjunction with an impact analytical model. This approach, however, can not be regarded as true prediction since it requires the fabrication of the entire sandwich and indentation tests to be made for various impactors and structures under consideration. The true prediction should possess the ability to predict the impact response from a knowledge of the behavior of the individual components of the sandwich panels as in Ref. [3]. Therefore, many of researches use finite element method to analyze the impact responses and predict the fracture initiation of

materials, however, simulation on post-failure behavior by FEM is rarely seen.. The objectives of this study is to develop a failure analysis procedure by FEM, which can investigate the failure modes and post-failure behavior of sandwich beam subjected to the cylindrical impactor. Maximum stress failure criterion and a modified stiffness degradation method are adopted to analyze the failure responses, and compared with the experimental results. After verification of this failure analysis procedure, parametric studies, including the stiffness ratio of face sheets to core and ratio of impactor diameter to simply-supported span are conducted as well.

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT TESTS

Sandwich panels made of laminated face sheets MAM (M : REM 300-65 glass mat; A : T-900 Aramid) and two DIVINYCELL core material with different density 0.1, 0.2 g/cm³ are taken into consideration. These sandwich panels are fabricated by IHI craft in Japan. The dimension of specimens is 9cm4.5cm and specimen are simply-supported at two edges with a span of 6 cm. The detailed description of test system and test procedure can be referred to Ref. [5]. As stated before by authors in Ref. [5], the main failure pattern of sandwich beam with foam core density of 0.1 is shear cracks in core material, located at some distance away from the impact point and with an inclined direction of 40~50 degrees. As the impact energy increases, the cracks will extend to the face-core interface, and then induce the delamination. The characteristic of impact force history when shear cracks occur is an sharp load drop. In contrast, when foam core density changed to 0.2, no shear cracks are found in core material, but crush in core and damage in top face sheets beneath the impact point are found, however, no abrupt load drop is shown in the impact force history. As mentioned above, it is evident that the core material has a great influence on failure modes, and for the sake of simplicity, the failure modes of sandwich beams with core density of 0.1 and 0.2 are named as Mode I and Mode II, respectively.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION AND DISCUSSION

The commercial finite element software ABAQUS and user-defined subroutine UMAT are used to simulate the failure behavior of sandwich beams. Because of the line load condition, the sandwich panels subjected to a cylindrical impactor can be modeled as 2-D plain strain problem. Since the core material dominates the failure behavior, an precise understanding of the response of core material to stress is required, especially the yielding or failure behavior. In Ref. [6], Shaw and Sata suggest that failure of foam is governed by the maximum principal stress, independent of the minor principal stress and that statement is strongly supported by Patel and Finnie in Ref. [7] and Zaslavsky in Ref. [8]. The micro-structure of foam considered in this study is similar to those used by Ref. [6]-[8], and due to the foam behavior which yields plastically under compression, but cracks under tension, the maximum principal stress failure criterion is chosen to predict the onset of cracks and yielding in foam core. The failure prediction and the algorithm as well as an illustration to modify the stiffness when core is degraded due to cracks or yielding are as follows;

When $\sigma_1 > X_t$, cracks occur, then E_1, G_{12}, ν_{12} are reduced to zero

When $\sigma_2 > X_c$, yielding occur, then E_2, G_{12} are modified depending on
the plastic behavior of foam material

where, X_t and X_c are the tensile and compressive stresses of foam core, respectively.

As for the face sheets, because the delamination and matrix crackings on laminated face sheets have little effects on failure mechanism, it can be reasonably ignored and only fibers damage is considered. When fibers damage occurs in tension or in compression, a degradation factor of 0.14 is used to modify the E_1 as suggested by Ref. [9].

STATIC TESTS SIMULATION

According to the phenomenon that the damage patterns of sandwich beams under dynamic condition are similar to those produced under static condition, thus, for saving the computing time, the check on performance of numerical failure analysis is conducted under static case.

Mode I

The typical static tests curve of sandwich beams indented by a cylindrical impactor is shown in Fig. 1. For convenience, several checkpoints are marked along the curve. Initially, the specimen is loaded up from checkpoint O to A, without any observable damage. Over the checkpoint A, minor matrix crackings on top face sheets and yielding of the core in the region underneath the indenter result in the reduction of bending stiffness of specimen. When the load path reaches B, the loading immediately drops from B to C due to the onset of shear cracks in core and the extension of cracks along the face-core interfaces. During the path CD, the specimen continuously deforms without further extreme failure. The comparison between numerical and experimental F-d curves is shown in Fig.2. It can be seen that those curves fit each other well. On the numerical F-d curve, there is a slight drop resulted from fibers breakage right over the level of A. This discrepancy is owing to the drawbacks of that method which simulates the fibers damage by multiplying a degradation factor right after the failed elements detected.

The progressive illustrations of simulation for shear cracks and yielding in core are shown in Fig.3, Fig.4, respectively. It can be concluded from Fig.3 that the progressive crack failure pattern is in consistence with the one observed during experiments.

Fig.1: The basic pattern of static indentation of sandwich beam with core density 0.1

Fig.2: The comparison on numerical and experimental results

Fig. 3: The progressive shear crack failure *Fig 4. The progressive yielding in core*

Mode II

When the core density is changed to 0.2, under the same configuration and loading condition, the failure patterns of sandwich beams are different from those of Mode I. From Fig. 5, the specimen is loaded from O to A without any failure, however, over the level of A, the core exhibits plastic behavior and face sheets are damaged in the region right under the indenter. As going further along the path AB, the degree of plasticity in core and damage in face sheets grows continuously. When checkpoint B is reached, fibers of top face sheets beneath the indenter are almost broken totally and a vertical crack located in the center line of the core is found. As the loading path moves, the crack propagates downward and the loading-carrying capacity of specimen loses gradually as seen in path BC. The comparison on computational and experimental F-d curves is shown in Fig.6. Although these curves are generally in consistent with each other, however, as mentioned before, the modeling on fibers damage needs to be further improved.

Fig. 6: The basic pattern of static indentation of sandwich beam with core density=0.2

Fig. 7: The comparison of numerical and experimental results

Dynamic impact analysis

After verification on static failure analysis of sandwich beam, the same failure analysis procedure is applied to the impact study. Due to the low velocity impact, effect of strain rate is not considered here. The mass of the impactor is 1.52Kg and the incident impact velocity is 2.174 m/s, making the impact energy 3.59 Joules. As expected, the failure patterns of sandwich beams with core density 0.1 and 0.2 are almost the same to those produced in static tests. Fig.7 shows the comparison on numerical and experimental impact force histories of sandwich beam with core density 0.1. It is evident that they fit each other very well.

COMPARISON ON STATIC AND DYNAMIC BEHAVIOR

As concluded above, under the low impact velocity considered in this study, the failure modes and failure patterns of dynamic cases can seem to be simulated from static cases. This conclusion can be further supported from the viewpoints of energy. In static case, the work done to specimens by the indenter can be obtained from integrating the force-displacement curve of the indenter. The amount of this work can also be regarded as the energy absorbed by specimens under the assumption of no energy loss. In dynamic case, there are two ways to calculate the energy absorption of specimens. (a) computing the loss of kinetic energy of the

projectile during impact (b) calculating the work done by the projectile in use of integrating the dynamic force-displacement curve of the projectile. These methods to evaluate the energy absorbed by sandwich beam are compared in Fig. 8. From Fig. 8, it is surprisingly shown that three curves fit each other very well. Further, at the same energy level, the energy absorbed curves are shown to be quite the same under various combinations; large mass impactor with low velocity and small mass one with high velocity. From the discussion above, it can be reasonably concluded that the dynamic behavior can be approximately simulated from the static one. For example, if the energy needed to move along the loading path from O to B as shown in Fig.2 is known, then the estimation whether the specimen will fail or not, for given impact velocity and mass of the impactor, can be done by comparing the static energy value with that of $1/2 mv^2$.

Fig. 7: The comparison on impact force histories

Fig. 8: The comparison on energy absorbed curves

PARAMETRIC STUDY

Core Material

Under the same face sheets MAM and geometric configuration, several sandwich beam with different core material densities are investigated. Core densities of 0.08, 0.1, 0.13, 0.16, 0.2 are taken into account and denoted by H80, H100, H130, H160, and H200, respectively. The elastic properties, yielding strength, and failure strength of each are listed in Table 1. The effective in-plane elastic property of face sheets is about 14.25 Gpa. The results of parametric study are tabulated as shown in Table2.

Table 1: Material properties of DIVINYCELL foam core

Core	E (MPa)	yielding strength (MPa)	failure strength (MPa)
H80	80	1.2	2.2
H100	115	2.0	2.75
H130	140	2.5	4.2
H160	170	3.4	5.1
H200	230	3.8	5.8

Table 2: Parametric study on core materials

Core	failure strength of sandwich(N)	energy needed to fail	failure mode
H80	1454	4.79	Mode I
H100	1874	4.51	Mode I
H130	1888	8.18	Mode II
H160	2066	6.86	Mode II
H200	2287	6.03	Mode II

From Table 2, it can be seen that the failure modes of sandwich beams with core H80, H100 are Mode I, the others are Mode II. Typically, no matter failure modes, the higher the core density is, the higher the failure strength of sandwich beam is. However, for the corresponding failure modes, the higher the core density is, the smaller the energy needed to fail is. These results show that sandwich with core material of higher density has better static fracture resistance, however, worse impact resistance from the viewpoint of energy.

Ratio of indenter diameter to span

The diameter (R) of the indenter is fixed to 1.2 cm, and the span (S) of simple support boundary condition are changed to 2 cm, 3 cm, 4 cm and 5 cm, thus, the corresponding ratio of R/S is 0.12, 0.15, 0.2 and 0.3. The results of parametric study are shown in Table3. Under the ratio of R/S considered, failure modes of all the sandwich beams are Mode I. As the ratio of R/S increases, the failure strength of specimen also increases, however, the opposite tendency is obtained from the energy viewpoint. Therefore, as the increase of ratio of R/S, sandwich beams have better static fracture resistance, but worse impact resistance.

CONCLUSION

To simulate the failure mechanism of sandwich beams subjected to a cylindrical impactor, the maximum principal stress criterion and a stiffness degradation method are coded into the user-defined subroutine UMAT provided by finite element software ABAQUS. This failure analysis procedure can precisely model two of different failure modes; Mode I: shear cracks in core and Mode II: yielding in core and damage in top face sheets right under the indenter. In the range of impact velocity considered in this study, it can be concluded that the dynamic behavior can be simulated from static results. The parametric studies on core density, and ratio of R/S are also conducted. The failure modes of sandwich beams with lower core density trend toward Mode I, whereas toward Mode II with higher core density, however, all the failure modes of sandwich beams are Mode I in the range of ratio of R/S considered in this study.

Table 3: Parametric study on ratio of R/S

R/S	failure strength of sandwich(N)	energy needed to fail	failure mode
.12	2219	6.048	Mode I
0.15	2389	4.51	Mode I
0.2	2639	4.173	Mode I
0.3	3222	4.085	Mode I

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